

KNOWLEDGE OF EPISTAXIS - DOCTOR'S PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Background: Epistaxis is a common problem that the vast majority of doctors have encountered throughout their professional careers. As an important cause of hospital visits, knowledge of the condition is necessary and steps to deal with this issue should be ingrained within a doctor's mind for appropriate management steps in a timely and orderly manner.

Objective: To assess the knowledge of young doctors regarding etiology and management of epistaxis and determine whether it meets the thresholds of adequacy

Methodology: A structured questionnaire assessing knowledge about epistaxis was provided to the doctors that met the inclusion criteria. The questionnaires were distributed mostly online and some were handed out to on duty doctors. The data from 108 doctors was compiled, statistical data tabulated and finalized. All the data collected was entered in SPSS ver: 17. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentage and the quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. Cross tabulation was done for knowledge and independent variables for statistical significance a p value of ≤ 0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

Results: The study showed that of 108 doctors of various hospitals in Pakistan vast majority of respondents had an adequate knowledge of causation of epistaxis (80.6%), however, many less respondents had adequate knowledge pertaining to management of epistaxis (49.1%). Amongst the respondents, whom had adequate knowledge of both causation and management of epistaxis (42.6%), there was considerable overlap amongst those who had adequate knowledge of management and those who had adequate knowledge of both management and causation, implying the majority of people who knew how to manage epistaxis

Conclusion: Most doctors have adequate knowledge regarding epistaxis. Many more doctors have adequate knowledge of causation of epistaxis as compared to management.

Key words: Epistaxis, young doctors, causation, management

Epistaxis or a nose bleed, as known by the lay man, is a menacing problem. It is extremely prevalent, affecting the majority of the population at one time or the other during their lifetime, having an estimated lifetime prevalence of 60% in the United

States,¹ of which 6% will receive medical attention.² Its bimodal distribution seems to affect those factions of the population (those below 10 and those above 50)^{3,4} in which management is particularly arduous. Compounding this problem, some researchers suggest that management of the common problem is poorly taught.^{5,6}

Epistaxis is a problem that most physicians will inevitably encounter, whether it be the primary problem or secondary to other disease processes.⁷ There is a myriad of situations in which epistaxis can present from a minor nose bleed in an ENT OPD to massive epistaxis in a patient presenting to the surgical emergency department and can be due to variety

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of different causes.^{8,9} It is absolutely essential that all doctors regardless of the field that they belong to have adequate knowledge of epistaxis so that they may promptly and appropriately manage the problem such as to alleviate the anxiety that goes hand in hand with epistaxis. Loaec et al. reported frequent epistaxis to be associated with a decrease in QOL index¹⁰ epistaxis was also associated with higher stress scores.¹¹

Not only are doctors the primary care takers of such patients but ultimately, they should be their teachers. A study conducted in Tabuk city¹² showed that there were no significant correlations between educational level and knowledge of cause and how to deal with epistaxis, meaning every individual regardless of education may benefit from the teaching of management of epistaxis. It is incumbent that doctors provide apt and necessary information to their patient regarding this common problem. However, this is not possible if the doctor has inadequate knowledge of epistaxis. They should be their primary educators regarding matters pertaining to health. However, there is a wide disconnect between doctors and patients in this regard.¹³ Most epistaxis stems as an outpatient problem, as such it is vital that first aid measures are known by the general population to decrease morbidity and mortality associated with this common problem and allay the misery of the patient by saving them considerable time and effort of repeated hospital visits. Indeed, first aid measures reduce morbidity and mortality in patients¹⁴ particularly in those with continuous bleeding.¹⁵

As such we think it necessary to gauge the knowledge of doctors regarding epistaxis and as such we have put together this article addressing the situation particularly focusing on young doctors that do not hold a post graduate degree as this group constitutes the major chunk of the work force and often have the very initial contact with patients. The objective of the study was to assess the knowledge of young doctors regarding etiology and management of epistaxis and determine whether it meets the

thresholds of adequacy.

METHODOLOGY

A Cross Sectional study was conducted at Allama Iqbal Medical College from April – June 2020. 108 young doctors of either gender, working for any duration in a clinical capacity in a tertiary care hospital public or private, in Lahore, Pakistan. The doctor must be consenting and carry MBBS degree or equivalent. Dentists, physiotherapists and doctors with post graduate degrees were excluded. A structured questionnaire assessing knowledge about epistaxis was provided to the doctors that met the inclusion criteria. The questionnaires were distributed mostly online and some were handed out to on duty doctors. The data from 108 doctors was compiled, statistical data tabulated and finalized. All the data collected was entered in SPSS ver: 17. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentage and the quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. Cross tabulation was done for knowledge and independent variables for statistical significance a p value of ≤ 0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

RESULTS

Although knowledge of epistaxis in general (e.g most common site of epistaxis) and knowledge regarding causes of epistaxis is very useful to any clinician or surgeon, knowledge of management of epistaxis is extremely necessary.

As such, our questionnaire focused mainly on the management of epistaxis however a handful of questions were also dedicated solely for the causation and general knowledge of epistaxis. Of the total questions: 3 related to causation of epistaxis from which a cumulative score was derived, the cumulative score looked into whether each individual had knowledge of the cause of epistaxis with any individual getting 2 out of 3 questions correct deemed to have adequate knowledge. However, if the question regarding risk factors of epistaxis was correct, the individual was deemed to have adequate

knowledge (even if the individual only managed to answer this particular question out of the 3 correctly). This was because it was felt unanimously by the authors that this question held enough weightage to deem the individual who answered this question to have adequate knowledge.

Whoever met the mentioned criteria was given a cumulative score of knowledge of cause $>/ 50$ (adequate). 12 questions of the questionnaire were focused on the management of epistaxis and a cumulative score of knowledge of management of epistaxis was given. An individual who correctly answered 6 or more of these questions was given a cumulative score of knowledge of management $>/ 50$ (adequate).

The study was conducted on a sample of 108 doctors of various hospitals in Pakistan out of which 65 (60.2%) were male and 43(39.8%) were female. The year of graduation of the correspondents fell in the range 2012 to 2019. of the 108 correspondents 52 (48.1%) were employed in medicine or its allied fields 40 (37.0%) employed in surgery or its allied fields & 16(14.8%) were general physicians. Only 26 (24%) had any work experience & out of these 13(12.0%) had 3 months (duration of HJ rotation) 13 (12%) had $>/ 1$ year experience working in ENT. 11(10.2%) respondents were currently working in a rural area and 93 (86.1%) were currently working in urban area. Also 2 (1.9%) were working in both.

There were 3 questions pertaining to the causes of epistaxis. 62(57.4%) were able to correctly identify the essential points in the history taking, the majority of respondents were able to correctly identify the most common cause of epistaxis with only 13(12.0%) incorrect responses and 47(43.5%) knew the % prevalence of epistaxis.

As a whole 80.6% had a cumulative score of knowledge of cause $>/ 50$ % and had knowledge regarding causation of epistaxis that met the threshold of adequacy, however, many less respondents had adequate knowledge pertaining to management of epistaxis (49.1%). Amongst the respondents, 42.6% had adequate knowledge of both causation

and management of epistaxis.

12 questions pertained to the management of epistaxis. Of the 108 respondents, 9 (8.3%) knew when an emergency referral to ENT was to be done and 14 (13.8) knew when an immediate emergency transfer was to be done. The majority of correspondents were aware of the correct site of nose pinching with 73(67.6) able to identify the correct option, only a few correspondents did not know the 1st step to control anterior epistaxis with 99(91.7%) answering the question correctly.

On the question regarding what the position of the patient should be during epistaxis 67(59.3%) were correct. When inquired on whether the blood from the nose should be spat out, collected or ingested, 86(79.6%) were able to answer appropriately. During the course of the research it was encouraging to find that the majority of individuals were able to correctly identify the 1st line antibiotics given to patients with epistaxis with 89(82.4%) answering correctly.

In contrast, few knew when prophylactic antibiotics should be used for epistaxis with only 14(12.9%) answering with the correct response. Similarly, only 49(45.4%) knew not to discharge a patient home after doing nasal packing. Of the test subjects, most did not know how long nasal packing should be kept in the nose for, as is reflected by the fact that 44(40.7%) were able to answer correctly.

We attempted to gauge their knowledge about cauterization of bleeding points in the nose and when it is indicated and when it is contraindicated. We found 9(8.3%) knew when cautery should be done whilst 10 (9.3%) knew when it is contraindicated. In total, 42.6% of the researched population had adequate knowledge of epistaxis. Only those who had adequate knowledge of both causation and management were considered to have adequate knowledge of epistaxis as a whole.

‘Knowledge’ of a subject is difficult to define and it is even harder to delineate the knowledge of a subject as either inadequate or adequate. Generally,

we found the results to show that the vast majority of respondents had an adequate knowledge of causation of epistaxis (80.6%), however, many less respondents had adequate knowledge pertaining to management of epistaxis (49.1%). Amongst the respondents, whom had adequate knowledge of both causation and management of epistaxis (42.6%), there was considerable overlap amongst those who had adequate knowledge of management and those whom had adequate knowledge of both management and causation, implying the majority of people who knew how to manage epistaxis were also aware of causation which is encouraging. In a similar study in Aseer,¹⁶ Saudia Arabia, it was found that amongst residents 23% had good knowledge about epistaxis. Slightly below half of respondents in our research (42.6%) were deemed to have adequate knowledge. However, their criteria to classify an individual as having 'good' knowledge was more restrictive as at least 60% of the total questions had to be answered correctly.

Although not directly linked to our research, it is fascinating to see how the different levels of medical education respond to the same question and it allows to gauge how medical knowledge matures. Therefore, we have included researches not only targeting doctors/medical personnel but also medical students and the general population.

The same study conducted in Aseer¹⁶ showed that only 56.4 % were able to identify the most common cause of epistaxis, whereas in our research 88% were able to identify the most common cause as trauma correctly. In a research conducted amongst medical students in Saudia Arabia¹⁷ only 40% were able to identify the most common cause of epistaxis. Albouq et al¹⁸ reported 87.1% incorrectly identified the most common cause of epistaxis as bleeding disorder, showing the disparity of knowledge even in the same country amongst medical students. A study¹⁹ conducted amongst the general population saw that 71.2% knew that nasal manipulation was a risk factor, in the same study 77.9% knew that environmental factors contributed to epistaxis. These

results are in contrast to findings in a study²⁰ of 600 respondents from amongst the general population, the large majority of whom did not know that medication or chronic disease were risk factors (74% and 82% respectively).

Alhejaily et al¹² conducted a study amongst the general population which showed that 34.8% knew that chronic disease causes epistaxis. 42.2% and 68.9% were aware of the fact that certain drugs and excessive nasal manipulation can cause epistaxis respectively.

Doctors in Aseer,¹⁶ outperformed doctors in our research when asked about relevant points in history taking, 66.3% of the doctors in Aseer were able to correctly recall relevant points to be asked in history compared to 57.4 % of doctors in our research.

When inquired about the position in which a patient of epistaxis should be managed in, 59.3% of respondents in our research were correct, much fewer than the 88.5% of patients in Aseer¹⁶ who were able to correctly identify the position. Our result was similar to that of Mugwe et al²¹ in which 60 % of the individuals identified the correct position.

When studying the knowledge of correct position in medical students we saw a significant number knew the correct position at 80.6%. Moving on to the general population, 45.2% knew the correct position to stop epistaxis in a study conducted in Tabuk⁽¹²⁾. Another study carried out amongst the general population²² showed that 56.9% of respondents knew the right position which was higher than the numbers reported by Strachan D and England J²³ at 36%. It was good to see 73(67.6%) of the respondents of our research were able to identify the correct site of nose pinching, at the other end of the spectrum only 38.1% of the respondents were able to correctly identify this point in a survey amongst clinical staff employed in Accident and Emergency in Kenya.²¹ Only 41.3% of medical students¹⁷ were aware of this site. One study¹³ found 15% of the general population knew the lower part of the nose should be pinched. Many studies showed that the general population knew that nasal compression was

beneficial in stopping bleeding with 55.6%,¹² 77.7%²⁰ of the respondents in different studies aware of this point.

An outstanding 91.7% of doctors in our research knew the correct initial step of controlling epistaxis, much greater than the 60.6% of the residents in Aseer.¹⁶

There were some limitations to our study. We had a relatively small sample size. Also, we did not include post graduates in our research. Some questions carry more value than others in that they must be known by all physicians and therefore they should have carried a higher mark in our scoring system.

CONCLUSION

Most doctors have adequate knowledge regarding epistaxis. Many more doctors have adequate knowledge of causation of epistaxis as compared to management.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Specialized workshops should be carried out to teach the management of epistaxis.
- Regular screening tests should be taken to assess doctor’s knowledge regarding epistaxis in order to gauge the effectiveness of such workshops and open-ended feedback should be encouraged to improve productivity and efficacy of such workshops.

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Variables n=108	Frequency		Percentage %	
	Correct	Incorrect	Correct	Incorrect
When should emergency referral to ENT be done?	9	99	8.3	91.7
When should an immediate emergency transfer to ENT be done?	14	94	13.8	86.2
What is the correct site of nose pinching?	73	35	67.6	32.4
What is the 1st step to control anterior epistaxis?	99	9	91.7	8.3
What is the correct position of the patient during epistaxis?	67	41	59.3	40.7
Should blood be spat out, collected or ingested?	86	22	79.6	20.4
What are the 1st line antibiotics given to patients with epistaxis?	89	19	82.4	17.6
When should prophylactic antibiotics be used for epistaxis?	14	94	12.9	87.1
Should a patient be discharged home after doing nasal packing?	49	59	45.4	54.6
How long should nasal packing be kept in the nose?	44	64	40.7	59.3
When should nasal cautery be done?	9	99	8.3	91.7
When should nasal cautery not be done?	10	98	9.3	90.7
Adequate knowledge pertaining to management of epistaxis (cumulative score of knowledge of management >/ 50 %) = 49.1%				

Variables	Frequency		Percentage %	
	Correct	Incorrect	Correct	Incorrect
What are the essential points in the history of a patient who presents with epistaxis?	62	46	57.4	42.6
What is the most common cause of epistaxis?	95	13	88	12
What is the % prevalence of epistaxis?	47	53	43.5	56.5
Adequate knowledge regarding causation of epistaxis (cumulative score of knowledge of cause >/ 50%) = 80.6%				
Adequate knowledge pertaining to management of epistaxis (cumulative score of knowledge of management >/ 50 %)				49.1%
Adequate knowledge regarding causation of epistaxis (cumulative score of knowledge of cause >/ 50%)				80.6%
Whom had adequate knowledge of both causation and management of epistaxis				42.6%

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